

Deliverable D11.1 Data portal and supporting API

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interface
BIA	BioImage Archive
FBbi	Biological Imaging Methods Ontology
FIB-SEM	Focused Ion Beam Scanning Electron Microscopy
FRET	Förster Resonance Energy Transfer
GA	Grant Agreement
HCS	High-Content Screening
IDR	Image Data Resource
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JSON-LD	JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data
NCBI	National Center for Biotechnology Information
OLS	Ontology Lookup Service
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
PU	Public (dissemination level)
REMBI	Recommended Metadata for Biological Images

RO-Crate	Research Object Crate
SEM	Scanning Electron Microscopy
SSBD	Systems Science of Biological Dynamics database
vEM	Volume Electron Microscopy
WP	Work Package
XNAT	Extensible Neuroimaging Archive Toolkit

Table of contents

Acronyms and Abbreviations	2
Table of contents	4
Executive Summary	5
1. Context	5
1.1 Purpose	5
1.2 Scope and non-goals	5
1.3 Position in the project	6
2. Approach	6
2.1 Design principles	6
2.2 The shared metadata model	7
2.3 RO-Crate as the exchange unit	7
2.4 Indexing and search	8
2.5 A two-tier specification	8
3. The portal and API	9
3.1 The catalogue indexing pipeline	9
3.2 The search API	9
3.3 The reference portal	12
3.4 Deployment and availability	13
3.5 Extensibility and outlook	14
4. Conclusion	14
References	14

Executive Summary

This deliverable reports on the GIDE bioimaging search system, which provides a search interface, accessible via both a data portal and underlying Application Programming Interface (API), that allows search over hundreds of imaging datasets held in independent, globally distributed resources. The system comprises three connected components: a catalogue indexing pipeline that ingests harmonised metadata from the participating resources; an API that exposes search across the resulting index; and a reference web portal, built on that API, that presents cross-resource search to end users. All three are complete and publicly deployed, with the reference portal available at <https://www.gide-project.org/portal> and the API at <https://www.gide-project.org/search/search>.

The system indexes metadata at the level of the imaging study (a collection of images) and draws on a data model that implements the minimal shared interoperability metadata set defined in WP7. Metadata is exchanged per dataset as detached RO-Crate, and indexed in Elasticsearch, with organism terms using the NCBI Taxonomy and imaging method terms using the Biological Imaging Methods Ontology (FBbi), with term labels resolved at ingest through the EBI Ontology Lookup Service. The index currently spans four sources behind three named resources, the Image Data Resource (IDR), BioImage Archive (BIA), and the two repositories that make up SSBD. A worked example shows a single query returning datasets from all four sources side by side, each linked back to its originating resource. The deliverable is a proof-of-concept demonstration rather than a production federation service, and its architecture is designed so that further resources, richer metadata, and additional portals can be added without redesign.

1. Context

1.1 Purpose

This deliverable reports on the data portal and supporting API developed in WP11. Together these components provide a cross-resource search system that represents the technical cumulation of foundingGIDE's bioimaging work. This report describes what was built, the design choices behind it, and how the components may be extended as further resources join the ecosystem. It is written to describe the system as delivered rather than as planned, and accordingly the present tense should be read as referring to the current deployment.

1.2 Scope and non-goals

The portal and API address discovery at the level of the imaging study or dataset, a collection of images sharing some common property (e.g. being those supporting a particular scientific result), which is the unit by which the participating resources organise their holdings. A search returns a link to the dataset in its original repository, together with the minimal core metadata that the GIDE consortium identified as valuable for discovery, tractable to extract across resources, and following the REMBI guidelines: title and description, contributing authors and organisations, the biological samples and organisms studied, the imaging methods used, associated publications and funding, and licensing and release information. Search may be filtered by source, organism, imaging method, licensing terms and release year, and individual datasets may be retrieved in full through the API.

Several capabilities lie outside the scope of this deliverable. The system indexes study-level metadata only; it does not capture or expose image-level metadata such as acquisition parameters for

individual planes or channels. Preclinical imaging platforms based on the XNAT architecture are addressed separately in WP12 and are not part of this portal. The deliverable is a proof-of-concept demonstration of shared discovery rather than a production federation service: WP10 establishes the groundwork for metadata exchange, and WP11 shows what that groundwork makes possible, but the indexing pipeline runs as a periodic snapshot process and not as a continuously synchronised live exchange. Finally, the system supports discovery and does not provide routes to deposit, or download the underlying image data, which continue to be served by the originating resources.

1.3 Position in the project

WP11 provides the final major output at the end of the project's bioimaging technical workstream and depends on the outputs of several preceding work packages. The shared ontologies identified through WP2's landscaping analysis, together with the gap analysis carried out in WP6 and reported in D6.1 informs the selection of those fields. The minimal shared interoperability metadata set established in WP7 and reported in D7.1 defines the core fields over which the portal searches. The groundwork for metadata exchange between the resources, carried out in WP10 and reported in D10.1, produces the harmonised metadata snapshot that the indexing pipeline consumes as its input.

2. Approach

2.1 Design principles

Four design choices shaped the approach taken:

1. Discovery operates at the level of the study. The participating resources differ widely in how they store and describe individual images, but each organises its holdings into studies or datasets that carry consistent descriptive metadata. Indexing at this level lets the system span heterogeneous resources, and validate that the approach is tractable before tackling the more challenging task of harmonising image-level representations.
2. Shared metadata should be a minimal core that every resource can populate. A discovery layer over autonomous archives is only as wide as its narrowest contributor: a field that one resource cannot supply is of little use as a common search facet. The model therefore captures the fields identified in WP7 as both useful for discovery and extractable across all sources, and treats richer description as optional rather than required. This principle is developed in Section 2.5.
3. Metadata should be expressed in a widely understood, standards-aligned vocabulary. The model is built on schema.org terms, using JSON-LD. This choice means the harmonised metadata is intelligible to consumers outside the project without reference to project-specific documentation, and it allows the four sources to converge on shared semantics without the project having to define and maintain a new vocabulary from first principles.
4. The shared search system provides read-only discovery over resources that remain authoritative for their own data. Each source remains the point of truth, and the portal directs users back to it.

2.2 The shared metadata model

The data model is a direct implementation of the minimal shared interoperability metadata set defined in WP7 and reported in D7.1. Where D7.1 specifies which fields constitute the shared core, the model realises those fields as a concrete, validated structure that the pipeline can populate and the index can store. The model is implemented in Python using Pydantic, and validates each record on ingestion so that malformed or incomplete metadata is caught before indexing.

The central entity is the Dataset, which corresponds to one study in a source resource. Its descriptive fields are drawn from schema.org, following good practices for structured web metadata. A dataset carries a name, a description, a date of publication, a licence, and a publisher; it lists its authors as Person entities, each of which may carry an affiliation and an identifier. The subjects of the study are recorded in an about field, which holds the biological samples and organisms imaged, and the experimental methods are recorded in a measurementMethod field, which holds the imaging protocols and techniques. Optional fields carry a stable identifier, descriptive keywords, associated funding as Grant entities, related publications, and an indication of dataset size.

Two of the model's entities are particularly important for bringing together the “biology” and “imaging” components of bioimaging. Biological samples are described by a BioSample entity, whose taxonomic range is expressed as one or more Taxon entities anchored to the NCBI Taxonomy. Imaging methods are expressed as terms anchored to the Biological Imaging Methods Ontology (FBbi). The ingest pipeline normalises these references on ingest. Taxonomy identifiers are rewritten to a canonical form, and FBbi identifiers are corrected to the capitalisation and zero-padding the ontology requires, which is easy to get wrong when metadata is prepared by hand. Human-readable labels are resolved at ingest by querying the EBI Ontology Lookup Service for each term and writing the returned label onto the record before it is indexed, so that the labels are stored in the index rather than fetched at query time. Throughout, the ontology identifier is retained as the canonical, stable reference. The effect is that controlled-vocabulary fields are held in the index in a consistent, resolvable form, with their ontology labels, regardless of small inconsistencies in how each source expresses them.

2.3 RO-Crate as the exchange unit

The harmonised metadata for each dataset is exchanged and ingested as an RO-Crate. RO-Crate is a lightweight, widely adopted convention for packaging research data and its metadata together, using schema.org terms expressed as JSON-LD. Using RO-Crate was a deliberate choice to enable wider interoperability with the research data ecosystem.

One alternative would have been live federation, in which the portal queries each resource's own API at search time and merges the results. This avoids holding a copy of the metadata, but makes portal responses highly sensitive to individual resource API latency, requires every resource to expose a query API of comparable capability, and makes consistent faceting across sources difficult because each resource would answer in its own terms. A second alternative would have been a single highly structured schema (e.g. using JSON schema) into which every resource's metadata is mapped by bespoke transformation. This centralises control but couples future metadata exchange tightly to that schema, makes each new source a schema-migration exercise, and discards the semantic context that makes the metadata reusable beyond the project.

RO-Crate provides a flexible solution. Because each dataset is a self-contained crate, sources can be ingested independently and a new source can be added without disturbing the others. Because the

format is an established community convention rather than a project invention, crates produced here remain meaningful to tools and consumers outside the project. The pipeline accordingly consumes one crate per dataset, validates it against the model, and transforms it into the form the index requires.

2.4 Indexing and search

The validated metadata is indexed in Elasticsearch. The portal required free-text search over descriptive fields combined with reliable faceted filtering over a small number of controlled fields, returned quickly and consistently across all sources. A search engine of this kind meets that requirement directly: it provides ranked full-text retrieval over titles, descriptions, and keywords, and at the same time supports exact aggregation over the fields used as facets, namely source, organism, imaging method, and release year.

Supporting faceted fields requires some transformation at ingest because they are derived rather than taken directly from the RO-Crate. The descriptive model holds organisms and imaging methods within the nested `about` and `measurementMethod` structures, which is the correct place for them semantically but not a convenient shape for aggregation. The indexing form of the record therefore adds flat, dedicated fields for the taxonomy and imaging-method identifiers, populated after validation by walking the nested structure and collecting the relevant terms, with imaging methods filtered to those anchored in FBbi. This keeps the descriptive model faithful to `schema.org` while giving the search layer the flat fields it needs for fast, exact faceting. The mechanics of this transformation are described in Section 3.1.

2.5 A two-tier specification

The model can be usefully understood as providing two tiers of metadata, to balance both ease of onboarding data resources, with specificity of search.

The first tier is a mandatory core that every indexed dataset must carry. A record is rejected at validation if it lacks a name, a description, a date of publication, a licence, a publisher, its authors, the subjects of the study, or the methods used. These are the fields without which a dataset is either not discoverable or not attributable, and requiring them guarantees that every record in the index supports the core discovery use case. This tier is deliberately small, so that the bar to a resource contributing its holdings is as low as possible while still supporting useful search.

The second tier is a recommended extended layer that records may carry but are not required to. Stable identifiers, keywords, funding, related publications, dataset size, and representative thumbnail images all fall here. These fields enrich discovery and presentation where a source can supply them, but their absence does not prevent a dataset from being indexed and found. Expressing the distinction in the validation model, rather than only in documentation, means the boundary between what is required and what is encouraged is unambiguous and is enforced uniformly across every source.

The value of the two-tier arrangement is that it lets resources join with the metadata they have today and enrich their contribution over time. A resource that can supply only the mandatory core is a full participant in search from the outset; a resource that can supply more sees its datasets presented more richly, without the project having to maintain separate models for different levels of completeness.

3. The portal and API

3.1 The catalogue indexing pipeline

The indexing pipeline takes the harmonised metadata produced through WP10 and turns it into a searchable index, in a sequence of stages that are run per source and can be repeated as sources are updated.

The pipeline first obtains the metadata for each source as a set of RO-Crates, one per dataset. For most sources the crates are produced by the WP10 exchange process; for the BioImage Archive the pipeline includes a dedicated transformer that builds crates from the resource's native metadata. Each crate is then validated against the data model described in Section 2.2, which both rejects records that lack the mandatory core and coerces the descriptive fields into the common structure. Validated records are transformed into the form the index requires, during which the flat faceting fields for taxonomy and imaging method are populated by walking the nested descriptive structure, as described in Section 2.4. The transformed records are finally indexed in bulk into Elasticsearch.

Figure 1: the catalogue indexing pipeline, and portal data flow

The pipeline draws metadata from four sources, although the foundingGIDE project plan names three. This is because SSBD is composed of two distinct repositories that are ingested separately: SSBD:database, the curated database of imaging datasets, and SSBD:repository, the broader repository of datasets associated with publications. The BioImage Archive and the Image Data Resource make up the other two sources. All four are represented in the index and are independently selectable as a search facet, so that a user may scope a search to any one of them or search across all four at once.

The pipeline is operated as a command-line tool. Each stage can be run independently, which allows a single source to be refreshed without reprocessing the others, and allows the index to be rebuilt from cached crates without re-fetching them from the resources. The metadata in the index is therefore a periodic snapshot of the participating resources rather than a continuously synchronised mirror.

3.2 The search API

The API exposes the index through a small set of endpoints and is documented through an interactive specification, so that a portal developer (or other API consumer) can discover and exercise it without reference to the source code. The API is available at <https://www.gide-project.org/search/search> and its interactive documentation at the /docs path of the same service.

The main endpoint is the search endpoint, which accepts a free-text query together with optional filters and returns a page of matching datasets. The filters correspond to the faceting fields: source, organism, imaging method, license, and a release-year range. Paging is controlled by a result count and an offset. A companion endpoint retrieves a single dataset in full by its identifier, and a health endpoint reports the service status for monitoring. The interactive documentation enumerates the parameters and response fields in full.

A search returns a list of hits, each of which carries the dataset's full descriptive metadata in the schema.org structure described in Section 2.2. Each hit pairs a stable identifier with an entry object holding the dataset itself: its title, description, publication date, and licence; its publisher as an Organization; its authors as Person entities identified where possible by ORCID; the subjects of the study under about, with biological samples carrying taxonomy terms anchored to the NCBI Taxonomy; and the methods under measurementMethod. Listing 1 shows one such hit in full, lightly abbreviated, so that the real response structure is visible rather than a flattened summary of it.

```
{
  "id": "https://idr.openmicroscopy.org/study/idr0167/",
  "entry": {
    "type": ["Dataset"],
    "name": "Predicting cell cycle stage from 3D single-cell
nuclear-stained images",
    "author": [{
      "id": "https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8501-8028",
      "type": ["Person"],
      "name": "Eva Nichols",
      "givenName": "Eva",
      "familyName": "Nichols"
    }],
    "description": "The cell cycle governs proliferation of all
eukaryotic cells [...]",
    "datePublished": "2026-03-30",
    "license": "https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/",
    "publisher": {
      "id": "https://idr.openmicroscopy.org/",
      "type": ["Organization"],
      "name": "Image Data Resource"
    },
    "about": [{
      "type": ["BioSample"],
      "name": "cell",
      "taxonomicRange": [{
        "id": "http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/NCBITaxon_10090",
        "type": ["Taxon"],
        "scientificName": "Mus musculus"
      }]
    }],
  },
}
```

```

"measurementMethod": [...]
}
}

```

Listing 1: a single search hit, abbreviated. The entry object is the full schema.org Dataset; the taxonomy reference resolves to a canonical NCBI Taxonomy identifier carrying its scientific name, and the author is identified by ORCID.

To make the cross-resource behaviour visible without reproducing ten full records, Table 1 reduces the first ten hits of an unfiltered query to one line each:

Source	Title (abbreviated)	Organism	Representative methods
Image Data Resource	Predicting cell cycle stage from 3D nuclear-stained images	Mus musculus	confocal, fluorescence, wide-field epi-fluorescence
Image Data Resource	Drug-Induced Phospholipidosis of repurposing libraries	Chlorocebus aethiops	spinning disk confocal (plus HCS protocols)
SSBD:repository	Isotonic minimally invasive optical clearing media	Homo sapiens, Mus musculus	recorded image
SSBD:repository	Intra-extra-nuclear and SUMO and PML	Cricetulus griseus, Homo sapiens	recorded image
SSBD:repository	Fluorescence images of myocytes in rat hearts	Rattus norvegicus	confocal laser scanning, electron microscopy
SSBD:repository	Dendritic compartment-specific spine formation	Mus musculus	recorded image

BioImage Archive	2D and 3D instance segmentation of nuclei from vEM	Homo sapiens, Mus musculus	FIB-SEM, SEM
SSBD:database	Visual quantification of prostaglandin E2 discharge	Canis lupus familiaris, Homo sapiens	FRET, fluorescence, time-lapse
SSBD:database	Dynamics of pollen tube in Arabidopsis thaliana	Arabidopsis thaliana	time-lapse, two-photon laser scanning
SSBD:database	Dynamics of radial axis formation in Arabidopsis zygote	NCBITaxon:3702	FBbi:00000253, spinning disk confocal

Table 1: the first ten hits of an unfiltered query, reduced to one line each, spanning all four sources.

The table highlights several notable features. The ten hits span all four sources, which demonstrates the primary function of the system: a single query searches across the participating resources and returns their datasets side by side, each linked back to its home resource. Second, organism and method values are for the most part presented as resolved ontology labels, for example "Mus musculus" and "scanning electron microscopy", rather than as bare identifiers. These labels are resolved at ingest by querying the EBI Ontology Lookup Service and are stored in the index alongside the canonical identifier, as described in Section 2.2. Third, the method lists highlight a wide range of imaging modalities, showing the heterogeneous nature of the participating resources' collections.

3.3 The reference portal

The reference portal provides a working demonstration, built on the API, that presents cross-resource search to an end user and shows the minimal core metadata for each dataset. It is a static web application built with the Astro framework and is deployed at <https://www.gide-project.org/portal>. The portal holds no metadata of its own; it is a client of the search API, which keeps the demonstration faithful to the architecture, in that anything the portal can do is something another consumer of the API could also do.

The portal presents a search interface over the full index, with the facets exposed as filters and results shown as a list of datasets carrying their core metadata and a representative thumbnail image where one is available. Selecting a result leads to a fuller view of the dataset's metadata and a link out to the originating resource. The figures below show the portal in use.

Search GIDE databases

Publisher

- BioImage-Archive (804)
- SSBd:database (248)
- SSBd:repository (151)
- IDR (143)

Organism

- Homo sapiens (443)
- Mus musculus (306)
- Mus musculus (121)
- Homo sapiens (72)
- Drosophila melanogaster (41)

[Show 10 more](#)

Imaging Method

- recorded image (389)
- fluorescence microscopy (343)
- confocal microscopy (303)
- bright-field microscopy (121)
- time lapse microscopy (120)

[Show 10 more](#)

Enter search terms... Search Page Size: Default

[Predicting cell cycle stage from 3D single-cell nuclear-stained images](#)

Identifier: [idr0167](#)

[Eva Nichols](#)

Published: 2026-03-30 Licence: [CC BY 4.0](#) Publisher: [Image Data Resource](#)

The cell cycle governs proliferation of all eukaryotic cells. Profiling cell cycle dynamics is therefore central to basic and biomedical research. However, current approaches to cell cycle profiling involve complex interventions that may confound experimental interpretation. We developed CellCycleNet, a machine learning (ML) workflow, to simplify cell cycle staging from fluorescent microscopy data with minimal experimenter intervention and cost. CellCycleNet accurately predicts cell cycle phase using only a fluorescent nuclear stain (DAPI) in fixed interphase cells. Using the Fucci2a cell cycle reporter system as ground truth, we collected two benchmarking image datasets and trained 2D and 3D ML models using support vector machine (SVM) and deep neural network architecture to classify nuclei in the G1 or S/G2 phases. Our results show that 3D CellCycleNet outperforms SVM models on each dataset. When trained on two image datasets simultaneously, CellCycleNet achieves the highest classification accuracy (AUROC of 0.94-0.95). Overall, we found that using 3D features, rather than 2D features alone, significantly improves classification performance for all model architectures. We released our image data, models, and software as a community resource.

Imaging Methods: [confocal microscopy](#) [fluorescence microscopy](#)

Organisms: [Mus musculus](#)

[Interdisciplinary Study on Drug-Induced-Phospholipidosis of](#)

Figure 2: portal landing and search interface

Search GIDE databases

Publisher

- BioImage-Archive (5)
- IDR (1)
- SSBd:repository (1)

Organism

- Homo sapiens (7)
- Canis lupus familiaris (1)

Imaging Method

- FRET (2)
- recorded image (1)
- fluorescence lifetime imaging microscopy (1)

Year Published

- 2025 (5)
- 2024 (1)
- 2023 (0)
- 2022 (0)
- 2021 (1)

fret Search Page Size: Default

[Database of FRET and bright-field images for H1975 cells co-expressing CFP-EGFR and YFP-GRB2 under drug treatment](#)

Identifier: [S-BIAD2405](#)

[Gao](#)

Published: 2025-11-17 Licence: [CC0](#) Publisher: [BioImage Archive](#)

This dataset comprises live-cell fluorescence resonance energy transfer (FRET) and corresponding bright-field images of H1975 cells co-expressing the fluorescently tagged proteins CFP-EGFR and YFP-GRB2 under various drug treatment conditions. The data were acquired using quantitative FRET microscopy to simultaneously capture dynamic drug-target interactions and morphological changes at single-cell resolution. This resource enables the quantitative analysis of drug-induced modulation of EGFR/GRB2 interactions, the correlation between target engagement and phenotypic outcomes, and the development of computational models for drug efficacy scoring. The dataset is an essential resource for researchers in cancer biology, drug discovery, and high-content image analysis, providing a foundation for studying dynamic protein-protein interactions and functional drug responses in a live-cell context.

Organisms: [Homo sapiens](#)

[Database of FRET and bright-field images for A549 cells co-expressing CFP-EGFR and YFP-GRB2 under drug treatment](#)

Identifier: [S-BIAD2406](#)

Figure 3: a search result listing showing datasets from more than one source, with facets applied.

3.4 Deployment and availability

Both components are deployed and publicly accessible. The API is served at <https://www.gide-project.org/search/search> with interactive documentation at its /docs path, and the reference portal at <https://www.gide-project.org/portal>. The source code for the search system, comprising the indexing pipeline and the API, is maintained at <https://github.com/foundingGIDE/gide-search>, and the source code for the reference portal at <https://github.com/foundingGIDE/gide-search-portal>. Both are released as open source under the Apache License 2.0.

The deployment reflects the deliverable's status as a public, reusable demonstration rather than a closed prototype: the API is documented for third-party consumption, the portal is one example consumer of it, and the open licensing allows other resources and other portals to build on the same foundation.

3.5 Extensibility and outlook

The architecture was chosen so that growth does not require redesign, and three directions of growth are worth noting.

A new source can be added independently of any existing ones. Because each dataset is exchanged as a self-contained RO-Crate validated against the shared model, onboarding a further resource is a matter of producing conformant crates for it, after which its datasets are indexed and become searchable alongside the rest. The four-source index demonstrates that sources with different native conventions, including the two distinct SSBD repositories, can be accommodated in this way.

The descriptive richness of the index can grow without a change to the mandatory contract. The two-tier model described in Section 2.5 means a resource that today supplies only the mandatory core can later supply more of the recommended fields, and those fields will be indexed and presented without any resource that has not done so being affected. The model can itself be extended with further optional fields as the shared metadata set evolves in later work, since the schema.org foundation provides established terms for many properties not yet used.

Finally, the demonstration points towards, without itself constituting, a production discovery service. The periodic-snapshot pipeline could be developed into a more frequently or continuously synchronised process (e.g. with databases pushing to it, rather than it pulling from databases); the single reference portal could be joined by other portals serving particular communities, all drawing on the same documented API.

4. Conclusion

This deliverable represents the culmination of the bioimaging technical stream of foundingGIDE, in which the work of several preceding work packages is brought together into a single working demonstration. The landscaping of ontologies in WP2, establishment in WP5, mapping and harmonisation in WP6, the minimal shared metadata set defined in WP7, and the metadata exchange groundwork of WP10 allow creation of a deployed, openly available system that lets a researcher search across four independent imaging sources through one interface and one shared model. In doing so it provides concrete evidence that the project's central aim, cross-resource discovery over a common minimal metadata set, is achievable in practice.

References

[1] foundingGIDE Consortium. D6.1: Report in metadata model overlap and gaps. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16794787>

[2] foundingGIDE Consortium. D7.1: Minimal shared interoperability metadata set. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20808012>

- [3] foundingGIDE Consortium. D10.1:Model description and snapshot. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20807591>
- [4] Pydantic. <https://docs.pydantic.dev/>
- [5] schema.org. <https://schema.org/>
- [6] NCBI Taxonomy. National Center for Biotechnology Information. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/taxonomy>
- [7] Biological Imaging Methods Ontology (FBbi). <https://obofoundry.org/ontology/fbbi>
- [8] Ontology Lookup Service (OLS), EMBL-EBI. <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols4>
- [9] JSON-LD 1.1. W3C Recommendation. <https://www.w3.org/TR/json-ld11/>
- [10] RO-Crate. <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/>
- [11] Elasticsearch. <https://www.elastic.co/elasticsearch>
- [12] Astro. <https://astro.build/>
- [13] foundingGIDE. gide-search source repository. <https://github.com/foundingGIDE/gide-search>
- [14] foundingGIDE. gide-search-portal source repository. <https://github.com/foundingGIDE/gide-search-portal>